

**On the Supposed Occurrence of Acids with Uneven
Number of Carbon Atoms in Vegetable Oils and
Fats. Part II. The Acid Fraction of Mean
Molecular Weight 354, from the Seeds of
Butea Frondosa (Roxb).***

BY U. S. KRISHNA RAO AND B. L. MANJUNATH.

During the examination of the fatty oil from the seeds of *Butea frondosa*, Katti and Manjunath (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 839) identified among the solid acids, palmitic and lignoceric acids only and isolated two fractions A and B, the first of which melted at 74.5-75.5° and had the mean mol. wt. 353 and the second melted at 77.5-79° and had the mean mol. wt. 383. The present investigation is concerned with the nature of the fraction A.

Katti and Manjunath (*loc. cit.*) found strong evidence in favour of the individuality of this fraction. They pointed out that *n*-tricosoic acid synthesised by Levene and Taylor (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1924, 59, 921) melted at 80-81° and that the lower melting point of the fraction A may be due to small admixtures of a lower acid and lignoceric acid.

Manjunath and Siddappa (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 495) have been unable to obtain any evidence regarding the existence of Daturic acid (C₁₇H₃₄O₂) in the oil of the seeds of *Datura stramonium*. Nöller, Milner and Garden (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 55, 1227) have separated the so-called 'Umbellulic acid' (Stillman and Neill, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1902, 28, 327) into capric and lauric acids. Since recent researches have thrown considerable doubt on the occurrence of acids with uneven number of carbon atoms in vegetable oils and fats, it was thought of interest to establish if the acid fraction A was really tricosoic acid or an eutectic mixture of acids.

* Taken from the thesis submitted by U. S. K. Rao for the degree of Master of Science in the University of Mysore.

EXPERIMENTAL.

25 G. of the purified acid A (m. p., 74·5-75·5°; M. W., 353) were esterified with methyl alcohol and the ester (m. p. 54-55°) was fractionated in high vacuum. The results confirmed the observations of Katti and Manjunath (*loc. cit.*). The acid liberated from the residues (2 g.) in the distillation flask on repeated crystallisation melted at 78-79°. Its molecular weight was 366. It did not depress the m. p. of pure lignoceric acid and its *p*-phenylphenacyl ester (m. p. 102-103°) and *p*-bromophenacyl ester (m.p. 93-94°) (Found: C, 68·1; H, 9·6. $C_{32}H_{53}O_3Br$ requires C, 68·0; H, 9·4 per cent) were found to be the same as those prepared from pure lignoceric acid.

Experiments were then made to prepare *p*-phenylphenacyl and *p*-bromophenacyl esters from fraction A. The former melted at 98·5-99° (Found: C, 80·9; H, 10·2. $C_{37}H_{56}O_3$ requires C, 81·0; H, 10·2 per cent) and the latter at 90·5° (Found: C, 67·5; H, 9·2. $C_{31}H_{51}O_3$ requires C, 67·5; H, 9·2 per cent). Repeated attempts at fractional crystallisation from various solvents did not effect any separation and the results appeared to point towards the individuality of A.

We may note here that the *p*-phenylphenacyl and *p*-bromophenacyl derivatives are unsuitable for the characterisation of the higher fatty acids as may be seen from the mixed melting points given below:

TABLE I.

No.	<i>p</i> -Phenylphenacyl ester of	M. p.	Mixed m. p. with
1	Palmitic acid	93-94°	(2) 90-90·5°; (4) 90-93°
2	Stearic acid	95·5-96·5°	
3	Behenic acid*	101-102°	(4) 98-99·5°; (5) 100-101°
4	Lignoceric acid	101-102°	(5) 100-100·5°
5	Fraction A	98·5-99°	

* (Found: C, 80·9; H, 10·3. $C_{36}H_{54}O_3$ requires C, 80·9; H, 10·1 per cent).

TABLE II

No.	<i>p</i> -Bromophenacyl ester of	M. p.	Mixed m.p. with
1	Palmitic acid*	83-84°	(2) 76-78°; (4) 84-86°
2	Stearic acid†	87.5-88.5°	
3	Behenic acid‡	93-94°	(4) 90.5-91°; (5) 91-92°
4	Lignoceric acid	93-94°	(5) 91-91.5°
5	Fraction A	90.5°	

Since identification in this manner proved inconclusive, the melting point curves of mixtures of palmitic and lignoceric acids, stearic and lignoceric acids were determined in order to find out if any evidence regarding the formation of an eutectic mixture could be obtained. Behenic acid for this purpose was prepared by the catalytic reduction of erucic acid** in the presence of nickel.

FIG. 1.

* (Found : C, 63.6; H, 8.1. $C_{24}H_{37}O_3$ Br requires C, 63.5; H, 8.2 per cent).

† (Found : C, 64.9; H, 8.7. $C_{26}H_{41}O_3$ Br requires C, 64.9; H, 8.6 per cent) Judefind and Reid (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, **42**, 1054) have prepared these two esters and give the melting point of the former as 81.5° and of the latter as 78.5°.

‡ (Found : C, 67.1; H, 9.2. $C_{30}H_{49}O_3$ Br requires C, 67.0; H, 9.1 per cent).

** *p*-Phenyl phenacyl ester, m. p., 72.5-73.5°. (Found : C, 81.3; H, 9.6. $C_{36}H_{53}O_3$ requires C, 81.2; H, 9.8 per cent).

p-Bromophenacyl ester, m. p. 60-60.5°. (Found; C, 67.4; H, 8.8. $C_{33}H_{47}O_3$ Br_x requires C, 67.3; H, 8.8 per cent).

From the three curves (Fig. 1-3) it became clear that behenic and lignoceric acids in equimolecular proportions form an eutectic mixture melting at 74-75°. Consequently an equimolecular mixture of behenic acid and lignoceric acid (m. p. 89.5; M. W., 370) was prepared and experiments were carried out to separate the synthetic mixture into its constituents.

Repeated crystallisations from various solvents, fractional precipitation of the lithium salts, or the high vacuum distillation of the methyl esters did not bring about any separation. In the last case as with A, a small amount of pure lignoceric acid was obtained from the residue in the flask.

(1) Repeated crystallisations from methyl and ethyl alcohols, acetone and ethyl acetate did not bring about a change either in the melting point or in the mean molecular weight.

(2) Fractional precipitation of the lithium salts also did not effect separation.

TABLE III.

Fraction No.	M. p. of acids liberated and crystallised.	Molecular weight.
1	75-76°	352.0
2	74-75.5°	354.2
3	74-75°	357.8
4	73.5-75°	357.0

(3) This mixture (22 g.) was converted into the methyl ester (23 g.) and the methyl ester (m. p. 55-56°) was fractionally distilled at a pressure of less than 1 mm.

Fraction No.	Range of temperature.	Wt. of fraction.	M. W. from sap. value	M. p. of acid liberated and crystallised.
1	below 198°	2.8 g.	352.2	74-75°
2	at 198°	6.1	356.7	74.5-75.5°
3	198-200°	7.2	354.9	74.5-75.5°
4	200-202°	4.0	358.3	75-76°
Residue		2.9		

A small quantity of pure lignoceric acid (2 g.) was obtained from the residue after saponification and repeated crystallisations.

Thus it was found impossible to effect satisfactory separation of the eutectic mixture of behenic and lignoceric acids.

CONCLUSION.

The fraction A is in all probability an eutectic mixture of behenic and naturally occurring lignoceric acids in equimolecular proportions and is not an individual substance. Similarly it is also highly probable that fraction B is an eutectic equimolecular mixture of lignoceric and cerotic acids. This latter acid has been found to occur sometimes in small quantities in vegetable products and forms probably another eutectic mixture of the type met with in fraction A.

As a result of this investigation the occurrence of behenic and cerotic acids in the oil of *Butea frondosa* is indicated.

We are indebted to Mr. P. Ramaswami Iyer for the lignoceric acid used in this investigation.